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EXPLORING THE OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES IN CROWDSHIPPING: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

In the last decade, there has been a growing trend in the last mile delivery – crowdshipping. Motivated by the ever-growing trend of online shopping and the rise of e-commerce with the last mile delivery becoming a very important aspect of distribution logistics, a review of selected scientific literature has been conducted. Last mile delivery tries to address the challenges and customer's attitudes toward parcel delivery. Hence, the implementation of new, sustainable ways to perform the last mile delivery is of high importance. The emphasis of the review was on the methods used for the implementation of the crowdshipping as a part of the last mile delivery. This study identifies the main crowdshipping service implementation challenges and risks, and proposes a future research agenda.

KEY WORDS: Crowdshipping; last mile delivery; method; risks; implementation.

INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving landscape of logistics, traditional supply chain models are being challenged by innovative approaches such as crowdshipping. It stands out as reshaping the way goods are transported and delivered. As urban last mile delivery providers are facing more and more challenges with the development of e-commerce, the advancement of smart communication technologies has stimulated the development of new business models for city logistics (Silva et al., 2023a). Since sustainable parcel transportation is one of the most crucial concepts of the smart city, many opportunities arose for environmentally friendly and sustainable delivery (Tsai et al., 2023).

Considering that in 2022 the number of shipped parcels has risen to the number of 161 billion, and is expected to reach 225 billion by 2028, last mile delivery providers are urged to include new, innovative, and sustainable solutions to overcome the ever-worsening levels of traffic congestion, air pollution, noise pollution, and other environmental impacts (Dietmann et al., n.d.). Crowdshipping is one of the sustainable and environmentally friendlier solutions as it does not create new trips, but uses pre-existing ones to carry out the parcel delivery to the end user. Since such delivery may include some risks and distrust, it is important to explore the challenges of such delivery. As last mile delivery is the costliest part that shipping companies endure, especially time-critical deliveries, companies are trying to mitigate this high cost by implementing crowdsourcing, using various delivery vehicles and types (Abualola et al., 2023).

Crowdshipping, sometimes referred to as crowd logistics, can be defined as a collaborative strategy that distributes delivery tasks to individuals who act as ordinary couriers reducing delivery costs and enhancing sustainability. Crowdshipping harnesses the unused capacity of individual's vehicles and travel routes to facilitate the movement of packages from one point to another. This model not only offers cost-effective solutions for businesses but also presents unique opportunities for individuals to monetize their resources (Pourrahmani et al., 2021), (Wang et al., 2023).

Crowdshipping was derived from the idea of crowdsourcing, where a large group of dispersed participants contribute in producing services for some monetary value or for free. Crowdshipping was first introduced in the early 2000s as a way for individuals to earn additional monetary compensation for moving packages or moving boxes. It was introduced as a quick, efficient, and

cheaper solution that does not require courier engagement which can be expensive and not as fast as the users would like. As a result, many startups have been created, especially in the US.

Crowdshipping, in its essence, presents enlisting members of the public to pick up and drop off parcels, ideally en route to their destination (Zhang et al., 2023). Most sustainable delivery options are via public transport (Wyrowski et al., 2024) and private vehicles, which represent occasional drivers, as crowdshippers can pick up the parcel on their commute. Another possibility is delivery via bicycle (Wicaksono et al., 2022), (Lin et al., 2020) which usually has capacity limitations.

Research shows that crowdshipping as a service can be optimized using various mathematical methods, simulations, different options for vehicle routing problems, machine learning, advantaging parcel lockers, using linear programming for creating algorithms, etc. As technology advances, it is expected to see more and more optimizations using artificial intelligence, machine learning, and Global Positioning System (GPS).

METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

The focus of this paper is the influence of crowdshipping on last mile delivery, the possibilities of optimizing the crowdshipping service, its opportunities and challenges, and research gaps. As crowdshipping is a fairly new model, it is still not known how dispersed this model is, how much is it used worldwide. However, there are several popular crowdshipping apps and startups that offer this service. They are mainly used in the US and some parts of Europe and Asia. Considering the influence of the transport industry on the environment, especially the last mile delivery, it is inevitable to implement new technologies that are environmentally friendly, lower emissions and reduce traffic congestion. Hence, the papers that were used in this research are fairly new, with most papers being published in 2023 after the COVID-19 pandemic, as seen in Figure 1.

To conceptualize the literature review, there is a predefined protocol to serve as a guiding frame for identifying and assessing the relevance of the studies (Sina Mohri et al., 2023), (Dohale et al., 2022). The definition and methodologies of crowdshipping, and the relation between crowdshipping and the last mile delivery were extensively researched within a period of 10 years, from 2014 to 2024. The research was conducted using scientific databases,

ScienceDirect of Elsevier and Web of Science (WoS) of Clarivate Analytics as shown in Table 1. After thorough research of all published papers that match the entered keywords and the removal of duplicate papers (that were found both at WoS and ScienceDirect), 59 papers were filtered out which are of interest for this paper.

Table 1. Published papers by keywords

Keywords / Database	ScienceDirect	Web of Science
Crowdshipping	124	80
Crowdshipping logistics	110	50
Crowdshipping AND last mile delivery	105	49
Crowdsourced shipping	171	30

Figure 1. A number of published papers taken into consideration for a review

SEGMENTATION OF THE PAPERS BY SOLVING TECHNIQUE AND THE PROPOSED SOLUTION

In this chapter, the authors delve into a comprehensive review of existing literature within the realm of crowdshipping, focusing on papers that have implemented methodologies using tools such as simulation approaches, linear

programming, and machine learning. Also, the papers that present the problem that can be solved by reducing to the vehicle routing problem or with the implementation of parcel lockers are taken into consideration. This paper focuses on exploring the methods of implementing and optimizing crowdshipping services, therefore, the research papers are segmented in this chapter by the solution methods.

Crowdshipping, as an emerging topic in logistics, has garnered significant attention due to its potential to revolutionize last mile delivery. The reviewed studies aim to address the complex challenges in crowdshipping operations, such as route optimization, resource allocation, and demand forecasting.

SIMULATION APPROACH

The simulation approach plays a vital role in the study and optimization of crowdshipping services. By modeling complex interactions and dynamics within the system, simulation provides valuable insight into the behavior and performance of crowdshipping operations under various scenarios and conditions. Simulation models aim to predict the performance of the solution in the real world by creating a digital prototype. Currently, the use of simulation models is of high importance, with agent-based simulation models and digital twins as preceding methods.

(Simoni et al., 2020) explore the potential impact of crowdshipping on traffic, considering factors such as transport mode, detour length, and parking behavior in a simulation-based analysis focused on Rome, Italy. Results highlight the importance of operational strategies, suggesting that while crowdshipping can reduce congestion and pollution, its sustainability depends on factors like mode choice, detour management, and incentivizing off-peak deliveries. Authors (Tsai et al., 2023) presented a trajectory feature extraction (TFE) algorithm and a task-to-crowd matching (T2CM) algorithm for precise assigning the delivery to the right crowd. Finally, they conducted a simulation based on the real-world dataset in three different scenarios.

(Galkin et al., 2020) present a comparative analysis between urban conventional delivery and green logistics solutions, developing an algorithm to select the most suitable technological delivery scheme based on economic and ecological factors. By addressing the multi-period nature of the problem and implementing strategies like request chaining and stochastic modeling, authors (Behrend et al., 2021) offer insights into improving operational

performance and consumer satisfaction in community-based sharing platforms.

Taking into account different fleets of vehicles for crowdshipping delivery in urban settings, authors (Dupljanin et al., 2019a) simulated real-world traffic conditions for analysis of delivery performance. Results showed that the bicycle-based crowdshipping fleet outperforms other vehicle types. Bicycles are presented as a faster, more environmentally friendly, and potentially cheaper alternative to traditional fleets. Authors (Abualola et al., 2023) address the challenge of last-mile delivery by proposing a hybrid framework that combines crowdsourced vehicles and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to improve delivery efficiency during peak hours.

(Dötterl et al., 2020b) address the high costs and challenges of last-mile parcel delivery; by utilizing an agent-based approach and smartphone sensor data, the system predicts delivery delays and strategically transfers parcels to nearby couriers, demonstrating the effectiveness of this method in preventing delays and enhancing on-time parcel delivery with crowds. While (Dötterl et al., 2020a) introduce a crowdshipping simulator that models crowd workers as autonomous agents making decisions on accepting delivery tasks based on shipping plans. Finally, authors (Chen et al., 2017) present the agent-based simulation to achieve a high level of service in cases of high or low supply/demand ratio and high or low detour time. Table 2 shows all relevant papers on integrating simulations as an operational approach for crowdshipping.

Table 2. Literature on papers using the simulation approach as an implemented methodology

Reference	Model	Strategy
(Simoni et al., 2020)	Hybrid dynamic traffic simulation	Creating macro and microscopic features of delivery operations
(Tsai et al., 2023)	TFE and T2CM algorithm	Solving job-to-crowd assignment problem
(Galkin et al., 2020)	Created algorithm for simulation of urban conventional delivery and green logistics solution	Creating an algorithm for choosing a scheme for cargo delivery

(Behrend et al., 2021)	Simulation using rolling horizon framework	Integrating item-sharing and crowdshipping on sharing platforms
(Dupljanin et al., 2019b)	A simulation approach for creating real-world traffic conditions	Comparing the performance of various fleet delivery performance
(Abualola et al., 2023)	Simulating a hybrid framework for the allocation of tasks and workers	Using task filtering, worker quality estimation, and task allocation to improve delivery time
(Chen et al., 2017)	Agent-based simulation model	Developed a model for assessing the supply/demand ratio and detour time
(Dötterl et al., 2020b)	Agent-based simulation model	Predicting delivery delays with smartphone sensors
(Dötterl et al., 2020a)	Agent-based simulation model	Presented simulator for workers' deciding to accept a delivery task

LINEAR PROGRAMMING

Linear programming, in its essence, is a mathematical concept that is used to find the most suitable solution for the linear function. A popular method is integer programming, in which some or all of the variables are integers. Authors (Baghestani et al., 2023) have presented a dynamic crowdshipping model to use the vacant space of taxis to deliver parcels while serving passengers. A mixed integer linear programming (MILP) model within a rolling horizon framework that periodically updates input information is formulated while the objective function aims to maximize the number of matched trips while controlling the total travel time in the system. Authors (Wang et al., 2023) also use mixed integer model for utilizing commuters' journeys to deliver parcels, introducing a joint optimization model for parcel allocation and delivery routing. By employing a data-driven column generation algorithm and a rolling-horizon approach, the study demonstrates significant efficiency gains and cost reductions, showcasing the benefits of joint optimization in improving last-mile delivery operations.

(Ghaderi et al., 2022) introduce a crowdsourced solution based on the Physical Internet concept, utilizing parcel lockers as exchange points for delivery tasks handled by individual or multiple crowdshippers. The proposed approach includes a novel model for locating parcel lockers and allocating delivery tasks, implemented through a two-phase algorithm that evaluates potential locker locations based on their utilization in cooperative delivery. Additionally, a selection algorithm with three strategies, considering both single and joint delivery scenarios. Retailers are addressing crowdshipping challenges by incentivizing their distribution center employees to deliver online orders on their commute home, ensuring reliable delivery services. They propose an exact solution using Benders decomposition, maximizing matched shipments while considering employees' minimum expected earnings per time unit, efficiently handling real-world sized instances before the end of a work shift for timely loading into employees' cars (Boysen et al., 2022).

The integration of in-store customers into same-day delivery services for online orders is proposed by (Dayarian et al., n.d.), addressing the uncertainty of delivery capacity and arrivals. Their proposed dispatching approaches, offer efficient solutions with potential benefits for same-day delivery, considering factors such as fleet size and arrival patterns to optimize service quality and operational costs. Sequentially, (Cheng et al., 2022) introduce a novel approach to optimize package deliveries in crowdsourced logistics by addressing the overlooked efforts of drivers, proposing a two-phase framework that integrates offline trajectory data mining and online route-and-schedule optimization to achieve high success rates and reduce taxi drivers' extra efforts. Table 3 shows all relevant papers on integrating linear programming as an operational approach for crowdshipping.

Table 3. Literature on papers using linear programming as an implemented methodology

Reference	Model	Strategy
(Ghaderi et al., 2022)	Two-phase algorithm	Using lockers as exchange points with algorithm ranking lockers and assigning jobs
(Boysen et al., 2022)	Benders decomposition	System of rewarding employees

(Baghestani et al., 2023)	Mixed integer	Using taxis to deliver parcels while serving passengers
(Dayarian et al., n.d.)	Two rolling horizon dispatching approaches	In-store customers deliver online orders on their way home
(Wang et al., 2023)	Rolling horizon approach	Utilizing the journeys of commuters to deliver parcels from intermediate station to customers
(Cheng et al., 2022)	Mixed integer	Optimizing delivery paths for taxis delivering parcels

TYPE OF VEHICLE ROUTING PROBLEM

The vehicle routing problem is a combinatorial optimization and integer programming problem based on the Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) with a goal of visiting all locations in the fastest and most optimal way. (Silva et al., 2023b) study the use of occasional drivers to complement company's fleet in the activity of delivering products to its customers. They model it as a variant of the stochastic capacitated vehicle routing problem propose an extended formulation for the problem using column-dependent rows and implement a branch-price-and-cut algorithm to solve it. For bigger instances of the problem, they have developed a heuristic approximation to cope with larger instances of the problem. Authors (Tao et al., 2023) focus on a last-mile delivery system that supports Online-to-Offline e-commerce partners for processing and fulfilling online orders in an urban area. Besides the full-time regular drivers, the system also relies on occasional drivers from society who dynamically announce their availability over the time horizon. They model the studied problem as a multi-depot pickup and delivery problem with dynamic occasional drivers. An event-based rolling horizon solution approach is proposed to solve the problem by iteratively calling for a re-optimization procedure to update the delivery plan at each decision epoch. Similarly, authors (Voigt et al., 2022) examine a scenario where a courier service utilizes both regular and occasional drivers, along with transshipment points, to optimize parcel deliveries. The problem, termed pickup and delivery problem with transshipments and occasional drivers (PDPTOD), is addressed using a mixed-integer programming model and an adaptive large neighborhood

search approach, revealing how the number and location of transshipment points influence cost advantages and the sensitivity of cost savings to flexibility and compensation schemes. Finally, (Martín-Santamaría et al., 2021) have also implemented Vehicle Routing Problem with Occasional Drivers (VRPOD), which seeks to minimize the total cost incurred to perform the deliveries using vehicles belonging to the company and occasionally hiring regular citizens to make just one delivery. However, the integration of these features into the distribution system of a company requires a fast and efficient algorithm. Another model, presented by (Wu et al., 2022), the two-echelon open vehicle routing problem with crowdshipping (2EOVRP-CS) utilizes a tangible nested genetic algorithm (NGA) to optimize crowdshipper selection, relay locations, and route planning. (Xiang et al., 2024) address the complexities of crowdshipping through the dynamic multi-vehicle pickup and delivery problem with crowdshippers (DMV-PDPC), introducing the attention model with the centralized vehicle network (AMCVN) method. Leveraging deep reinforcement learning, AMCVN integrates a centralized vehicle network (CVN) to monitor vehicle states and enhance performance, with the attention-based route-generating network (RGN) determining optimal routes.

Authors (Behrend et al., 2019) are using the item-sharing and crowdshipping problem with an aim to optimize item fulfillment and transportation by private individuals. Generalizing the problem to include crowdshippers' capacity, the study proposes an exact solution method based on set packing, with experiments demonstrating the advantages of higher crowdshipper capacities and the efficiency of the proposed method compared to previous approaches.

(Sampaio et al., 2020) discuss the emergence of innovative delivery models in urban areas, such as crowdshipping, and explore the potential benefits of introducing transfers in the delivery system, framing the problem as a multi depot pickup and delivery problem with time windows and transfers. (Xiang et al., 2023) tackle the complex dynamic routing problem involving both crowd-sourced drivers and company vehicles to minimize total costs while ensuring a certain service level. By introducing a hierarchical reinforcement learning method, it balances opportunities and risks, resulting in superior solution quality, computation time, and generalization ability compared to existing methods, as demonstrated through extensive numerical analyses.

A scenario where a crowd-shipping platform utilizes both professionally driven vehicles and occasional drivers to fulfill diverse delivery requests from a central depot requires an optimization of route acceptance and ensuring

efficient delivery. The problem is formulated as a two-stage stochastic model with route duration constraints and compensation considerations. Hence, a branch-and-price algorithm is proposed for solving smaller instances, while a heuristic is developed for larger instances, with the complexity reduced by setting an upper bound on the number of occasional drivers (Torres et al., 2022). (Archetti et al., 2016) aim to minimize total costs of vehicle use and occasional driver compensations by a multi-start heuristic implemented to address the resulting variant of the capacitated vehicle routing problem. It produces solutions close to optimal ones obtained through integer programming. Finally, all related articles are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Literature on papers using vehicle routing problem as an implemented methodology

Reference	Model	Strategy
(Silva et al., 2023b)	Stochastic capacitated VRP	Using VRP to model existing fleet and occasional drivers
(Tao et al., 2023)	Pickup-and-delivery problem	Rolling horizon solution was used for re-optimization of the delivery plan
(Behrend et al., 2019)	Detour routing problem	Routing crowdshippers through intermediate locations
(Voigt et al., 2022)	PDPTOD	Created a new VRP model for integrating occasional drivers in existing transshipment points
(Torres et al., 2022)	Branch-and-price algorithm	Creating a VRP model for reducing pricing problems in delivery constraints
(Martín-Santamaría et al., 2021)	VRPOD	Minimizing the total cost for crowdshipping and company deliveries
(Xiang et al., 2023)	Dynamic routing problem	Minimizing the total cost for crowdshipping and company deliveries

(Wu et al., 2022)	2EOVRP-CS	Creating a model for a three-part delivery
(Xiang et al., 2024)	DMV-PDPC	Monitoring all vehicles and choosing one for delivery
(Archetti et al., 2016)	CVRP	Using the VRP model for implementing occasional drivers in the delivery plan
(Sampaio et al., 2020)	PDPTW-T	Implementing transfers to support delivery driver activities

MACHINE LEARNING

Machine learning is a branch of Artificial Intelligence that creates programs, with the use of data and algorithms, that offer solutions without the additional programming. Most authors use deep reinforcement learning algorithms (DRL) for the implementation of crowdsourcing in delivery systems, or for creating crowdshipping sustainable solutions. (Silva et al., 2023a) analyze different recourse strategies and compare them to exact approach solutions. Computational results demonstrate that DRL is capable of making appropriate decisions throughout the day resulting in optimized solutions that reduce total costs. The authors (Silva et al., 2022) were able to show the advantages of implementing an alternative to flexible compensation fees. (Parvez Farazi et al., 2022) introduce a DRL solution for dynamic crowdshipping, utilizing heuristics-embedded Deep Q-Network (DQN) algorithms to optimize delivery assignments and minimize costs, achieving a significant reduction of shipping costs by 24-37% compared to conventional heuristic methods. Analyzing real-world crowdshipping data, it compares deep learning models for short-term trip prediction, showing ConvLSTM's superior performance, and emphasizing the significance of capturing both spatial and temporal features for accurate predictions, authors (Shen et al., 2020) investigate crowdshipping dynamic in Atlanta, revealing its pricing advantages over FedEx and disparities between sender and courier preferences.

(Ahamed et al., 2021) address a novel deep reinforcement learning approach to achieve improved efficiency, convergence, and stability in training. By characterizing system states comprehensively and embedding heuristic strategies, including rule-interposing to prevent route repetition. To improve

service quality, (Bruns et al., 2023) propose adaptive task transfers, though implementing them is complex due to autonomous workers and uncertain outcomes. The proposed mechanisms include data stream learning for outcome prediction and two task coordination approaches: an opportunistic model for collaborative but non-autonomous workers in crowdshipping and a market-based model for autonomous workers in crowdsensing. Used for classification and regression, random forest machine learning can predict shipment status and identify key factors, therefore authors (Ermagun et al., 2020) show results that indicate that context plays a crucial role in predicting performance, informing the design of incentives and customer-tailored smartphone applications to improve delivery probabilities, with pricing and timing emerging as significant factors. Table 5 shows all relevant papers on integrating machine learning as an operational approach for crowdshipping.

Table 5. Literature on papers using machine learning as an implemented methodology

Reference	Model	Strategy
(Silva et al., 2023a)	Deep reinforcement learning algorithm	Capturing uncertainty due to online orders and occasional drivers
(Silva et al., 2022)	Deep reinforcement learning algorithm	Creating a compensational scheme for occasional drivers
(Parvez Farazi et al., 2022)	Deep reinforcement learning algorithm	Using DQN for on-demand crowdshipping
(Shen et al., 2020)	Deep reinforcement learning algorithm	Predicting short-term delivery trip production
(Ahamed et al., 2021)	Deep reinforcement learning algorithm	Using DQN for efficient carrying capacity and delivery time availability
(Bruns et al., 2023)	Data stream learning algorithm	Creating two approaches for task coordination and outcome prediction
(Ermagun et al., 2020)	Random forest machine learning algorithm	Predicting crowdshipping delivery performance

USE OF PARCEL LOCKERS

Parcel lockers play a pivotal role in the ecosystem of crowdshipping by providing secure and convenient locations for the exchange of goods between senders and couriers. These lockers represent intermediary points where packages can be deposited and retrieved at the courier's convenience. They represent efficient and contactless transactions. Integrated with digital platforms, parcel lockers streamline the logistics process, enhancing transparency and reliability while minimizing the need for direct interaction between parties. Furthermore, the widespread deployment of parcel lockers contributes to the scalability and accessibility of crowdshipping networks, enabling seamless integration into urban environments and enhancing last mile delivery capabilities.

Many authors in their research papers use the convenience of parcel lockers. They are mostly used as exchange points (Simoni et al., 2020), (Fessler et al., 2024), and in the research by (Ghaderi et al., 2022), parcel lockers are located using a new model to allocate delivery tasks. The parcel lockers are ranked and chosen by a crowdshipper based on the type of delivery, single or joint. Parcel lockers present delivery points with a high positive effect on acceptance since they offer flexibility in delivery times (Cebeci, Tapia, Nadi, et al., 2023). Furthermore, authors (Oliveira et al., 2022) constructed a model of connecting parcel lockers to the population by minimizing the maximum distance between each other. i.e., the population would be able to reach the lockers within a 10-minute cycling ride. Also, the locker network was made accessible to public transportation and micromobility users.

Authors (Fessler, Cash, et al., 2023) presented a case study taking place in Denmark with the use of automated parcel lockers that were placed at public transportation stations. The app was created for the purpose of relocating parcels from one locker to another. Authors (Gatta, Marcucci, Nigro, & Serafini, 2019), (Gatta, Marcucci, Nigro, Patella, et al., 2019), have also used automated parcel lockers in their case study located inside the transit stations with the goal of lowering congestion and pollution due to the dedicated trips performed by motorized vehicles.

REVIEW OF SCIENTIFIC PAPERS

Figure 2 shows the segmentation of the papers used in this research by the solution technique of the proposed solution. Based on this summary table, it

is visible that most papers use some type of Vehicle Routing Problem to reduce their problem. Because of its versatility, it is widely used in last mile delivery optimization, and in this case, crowdshipping implementation. Nevertheless, with the ever-growing technology development, machine learning will likely be used even more often as last mile delivery is very susceptible to change in real time.

Figure 2. Segmentation of the reviewed papers

CROWDSHIPPING SERVICES' CHALLENGES

Implementing crowdshipping, and extending last-mile delivery service to public individuals, may bring some risks for companies. These may be damaged parcels, missing parcels, late deliveries, increased motor vehicle emissions, etc. Authors (Bajec et al., 2022) through the research of three stakeholders, the owner of the crowdshipping platform, crowdshippers and the company that issued the parcel, tried to maximize the profitability of the platform, minimize environmental pollution, and enhance the quality of delivery. They have implemented a leader-follower game to provide sustainable delivery with a balance between costs and profits (Pahwa et al., 2022). Although crowdshipping is regarded as a sustainable freight solution, it is important to assess the feasibility and environmental impact of using private vehicles for delivery (Dai et al., 2020), (de Oliveira Leite Nascimento et al., 2023). Using crowdshipping services may lower delivery prices while offering instant shipping; authors (Bai et al., 2024) used an algorithm for

cooperative game-based cost allocation which achieved a 10% decrease in delivery fees and a 3% increase in completion rates with poor service quality. Using on-demand mobility services with parcel delivery service providers showed achieving 17% cost savings and 15.8% profit improvement (Peng et al., 2024), (Akbar et al., 2024). Authors (Zhang et al., 2023) compared the performance of carriers with and without crowdshipping and presented results as crowdshipping reduces vehicle distance and air emissions by 17%, and reduces carrier's delivery costs by 29% per parcel. Another research (Zhang et al., 2024) showed that by using crowdshipping, couriers can reduce carbon dioxide emissions and distance traveled by 20%, with the possibility that 11% of parcels can be redirected for a crowdshipping delivery.

The research showed that willingness to participate in the crowdshipping depends on the motivational factors (Upadhyay et al., 2022). Generation "Z" found more enjoyment and willingness to participate in crowdshipping for sustainable last mile delivery. They are frequent users of digital technology and are engaged on social media platforms in order to establish a social network. Apart from the generational division of willingness to participate, authors (Cebeci, Tapia, Nadi, et al., 2023) tested the willingness to deliver parcels in commute-based and home-based trips in low-income and high-income groups of crowdshippers. The research showed that the low-income group of participants have a lower value of time and show a willingness to make a detour to execute a delivery. Similarly, younger people, particularly students, showed a higher intention to participate in crowdshipping services (Fessler et al., 2024). Authors (Mohri et al., 2024) conducted research between several classes of possible crowdshipping participants. The research showed that employed citizens of higher age who don't use public transportation often, are willing to participate in crowdshipping as long as they are not logistically burdensome. Furthermore, younger participants who are less sensitive to task difficulty are willing to participate in crowdshipping with minimum incentives. Finally, participants who use public transportation on a regular basis and with high incomes, are unwilling to participate in crowdshipping unless they are well compensated. Similar results were found in (Fessler, Klöckner, et al., 2023), (Miller et al., 2017), (Punel et al., 2019). It is also important to take into account the willingness of occasional drivers to participate in crowdshipping delivery, considering the monetary compensation (Neudoerfer et al., 2021), as well as the willingness of requesters to pay for their parcels to be picked up and delivered by a crowdshipper (Allahviranloo et al., 2019).

Besides cost and willingness to participate in crowdshipping services, another important aspect is trust and safety. (Cebeci, Tapia, Kroesen, et al., 2023) conducted research on including trust in a correct delivery. Trust has a partially mediating effect on the adoption of the service and an effect on adoption via reputation and damage.

CONCLUSION

Although crowdshipping is a relatively new delivery service, it presents a sustainable, economical, and ecologically friendly system, while it also presents issues with very scarce information on delivery security, the willingness of crowdshippers to perform deliveries, and cost formation. It is also important to take into account the buyers' trust in crowdshipper while performing delivery. There are many ways to optimize crowdshipping delivery, using mathematical methodologies and routing problems, linear programming, machine learning, etc. It can only be assumed that the models used in the optimization and organization of crowdshipping services will more depend on artificial intelligence and machine learning while using a form of vehicle routing problem. It is important to take machine learning and the development of AI into consideration as crowdshipping and last mile delivery depend on the real-time data

The relationship between crowdshipping and courier companies should be explored, including feasibility, risks, and safety. There are not many papers that provide research on parcel safety and ensuring that the customer receives their ordered parcel. Furthermore, as some private information about the sender and receiver is oftentimes on the parcel label, there is a research gap in exploring the risk of breach of private information. Even though some authors mentioned that crowdshipping parcels do not contain personal information, it can be assumed that this parcel was prepared upfront. If a parcel was delivered to a parcel locker, it may contain personal information, which can be detected once a crowdshipper picks up the parcel for delivery to the customer.

Since last mile delivery is usually the most expensive aspect of logistics, door deliveries will likely become a luxury, and parcel lockers and crowdshipping will become more and more popular and requested as a service. It should also extensively explore the possibility of connecting taxi driving with crowdshipping. Furthermore, some companies are already using autonomous vehicles for providing taxi services, as well as item-sharing and

crowdshipping. The research on these companies is very scarce, so the future of such services should be of great interest to future researchers.

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